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STOMATOPODA

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L U N D
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The Stomatopoda of Chile are comparatively few and our collection is not large. It consists of four species, one of which is new to science. In the case of one of the other three, *Squilla armata*, the present collection considerably extends our knowledge of the range of morphological variation.

Species obtained

Squilla armata H. MILNE-EDWARDS

St. M 20. Golfo de Ancud, northern part, Estero Huito. $41^{\circ}43'50''$ S., $73^{\circ}10'15''$ W. 15 m. Very fine sand mixed with mud. 15. XII.1948. 1 specimen.

St. M 29. Seno Reloncaví, Estero Reloncaví, Bahía Ralún. $41^{\circ}24'30''$ S, $72^{\circ}19'45''$ W. 35—40 m. Very fine, clay-like sand. 4.I.1949. 10 specimens.

St. M 46. Golfo de Ancud, northern part, Canal Caicaen. $41^{\circ}46'15''$ S, $73^{\circ}09'00''$ W. 13 m. Coarse sand. 25.I.1949. 2 specimens.

St. M 83. Seno Reloncaví, Estero Reloncaví, W of Río Puelo. $41^{\circ}38'05''$ S, $72^{\circ}20'45''$ W. Abt. 170 m. Very fine mud, mixed with sand. 31.III.1949. 1 specimen.

St. M 86. Seno Reloncaví, Estero Reloncaví, W of Relonhué. $41^{\circ}28'40''$ S, $72^{\circ}19'25''$ W. 100 m. Sand with a little mud and some stones. 31.III.1949. 4 specimens.

St. M 107. Golfo de Ancud, N of Punta Barranco at Isla Abtao, $41^{\circ}47'18''$ S, $73^{\circ}20'55''$ W. 60 m. Coarse sand with mud and some dead algae. 5.V.1949. 8 specimens.

St. M 163. Central Chile, Bahía de Concepción, SE of Isla Quiriquina. $36^{\circ}40'15''$ S, $73^{\circ}01'48''$ W. 20 m. Soft bottom. 10.XII.1948. 1 specimen.

Distribution. Chile from Valparaiso to Cape Horn, Atlantic coast of Patagonia, SW and S Africa, S Australia, New Zealand. Bathymetrical range (according to SCHMITT 1940 p. 151) abt. 80—220 m.

As will be seen from the list of localities our collection of the species considerably extends its bathymetrical range towards shallow water, the upper limit noted by us being 13 m.

It will also be seen that the species apparently shows a predilection for bottoms mixed with sand, a purely muddy and clayey substrate being avoided. On the other hand it was collected twice on bottoms of coarse sand.

The general distribution of the species which is antiboreal circumpolar in moderate depths is interesting and a splitting up of the species into subspecies in the various

Table 1

Squilla armata, survey of individual variations with respect to certain morphological features.

Station	Length mm.	Spines on rapt. dactylus	Spines on hind marg. of 5th abd. segm.		Denticles on telson		
			right	left			
♂♂							
M 20	145	7	0	0	0	9	1
M 163	108	7	1	2	0	11	1
M 83	84	7	1	1	0	10	1
M 46	80	10	0	0	0	12	1
M 86	61	6	2	2	0	10	1
M 86	abt. 60	8	—	—	—	—	—
M 29	59	6	1	1	0	8	1
M 107	53	7	1	1	0	11	1
M 86	52	9	2	1	0	9	1
M 29	50	8	1	1	0	12	1
M 29	abt. 50	7	—	—	—	—	—
M 107	49	8	0	0	0	11	1
M 29	43	7	0	0	0	11	1
M 29	43	7	0	0	0	11	1
M 107	abt. 40	9	—	—	—	—	—
♀♀							
M 46	119	9	2	2	0	10	1
M 86	68	6	0	0	0	11	1
M 29	52	6	0	0	0	10	1
M 107	48	8	0	0	0	12	1
M 29	48	7	1	1	0	11	1
M 107	46	8	1	0	0	10	1
M 29	43	6	0	0	0	11	1
M 107	42	9	0	0	0	12	1
Sex?							
M 107	33	8	0	0	0	10	1
M 107	32	8	1	2	6	14	1
M 29	24	8	0	0	4	11	1
M 29	20	7	0	0	12	15	1

widely separated areas of occurrence would not be surprising. However, with our present knowledge of the species such a sub-division cannot be made. In order to provide a starting point for future investigators an analysis of certain morphological features of the 27 specimens of our collection was made. The result will be seen in table 1.

Some interesting facts emerge from the table. It will be seen immediately that

there exists no correlation between the size of the specimen and the armature of the raptorial dactylus or the posterior margin of the 5th abdominal segment. Nor is there any direct correlation between the size of the specimen and the number of denticles of the telson. However, the earliest stages obtained by us had not yet attained the adult type of telson but still possessed a telson of postlarval type. The largest specimen with a larval telson (*St. M 107*) had a total length of 32 mm, while the smallest specimen with telson of adult type (same locality) was 33 mm long. No sexual differences seem to be present as far as the investigated features are concerned.

Only from two localities are more than a few specimens at my disposal, viz. from *St. M 29* (Bahía Ralún in the innermost part of the very long fjord Estero Reloncaví) and *St. M 107* (Isla Abtao in the open Golfo de Ancud). As will be seen from the comparison below there exists possibly a significant difference between the number of spines on the raptorial dactylus of the two populations.

Number of spines on rapt. dactylus

	6	7	8	9	Mean
Specimens <i>M 29</i>	3	5	2	—	6.9 ± 0.7
Specimens <i>M 107</i>	—	1	5	2	8.1 ± 0.6

This would seem to indicate that despite of the fact that the species has a pelagic development a population inhabiting a long and narrow fjord like the Estero Reloncaví may be more or less isolated. It is rather probable that the pelagic larvae will be carried backwards and forwards with the rhythm of the tides inside the fjord but that there is really little interchange between the populations within and without. *S. armata* was found in two more localities within the fjord (*St. M 83* and *St. M 86*) and in two more in the Golfo de Ancud not far from *St. M 107* (*St. M 20* and *St. M 46*). A comparison of the armature on the raptorial dactylus of all the specimens from the fjord and the gulf gives the following result.

Number of spines on raptorial dactylus

	6	7	8	9	10	Mean
Estero Reloncaví	4	6	3	1	—	7.1 ± 0.9
Golfo de Ancud	—	2	5	3	1	8.3 ± 0.9

This result rather supports the suggestion made above.

The characteristic group of spines between the submedian and the intermediate carina on the hind margin of the fifth abdominal segment is said by SCHMITT (1940 p. 140) to consist of 1—4 spines while numerous S. African specimens examined by

BARNARD (1950 p. 846) possess no such spines. As seen from table 1 none of the present specimens has more than 2 spines and about half of them lack spines altogether. It may be worth mentioning that a specimen 32 mm in length which has still a telson of a postlarval type is provided with one spine on the right side and two spines on the left side of the fifth segment.

With respect to the features investigated the specimens from the part of Chile dealt with here are covered by the following diagnosis: Spines of raptorial dactylus (including terminal spine) 6—10, number of spines between submedian and intermediate carina on posterior border of fifth abdominal segment 0—2, denticles of the telson 0, (8—) 10—12, 1, submedian denticles often represented by fine crenulation or minute spines, frequently in asymmetrical arrangement.

Pseudosquilla lessoni (GUÉRIN).

St. M 125. Northern Chile, Coquimbo area, Bahía Herradura de Guayacán, south-western corner, NW of Herradura. 29°58'51" S, 71°22'56" W. Tidal belt. Boulders, stones, and sand. 22.VI.1949. 1 defective specimen.

Of this species only the larger part of the abdomen of one specimen was obtained. It was found by Dr. L. B. HOLTHUIS in our collection of Decapoda Natantia, and was determined by him. It does not extend the known range of the species.

Distribution. A West American species occurring from Wilmington in California to Juan Fernandez and Puerto Montt in Chile.

Hemisquilla styliifera (H. MILNE-EDWARDS).

Central Chile, Valparaiso area, Marine Biological Station at Montemar. 32°57' S, 71°33' W. 1950. 1 specimen 163 mm in length, presented by the Marine Biological Station.

Distribution. From California (San Pedro) and (possibly) Hawaii (cf. BALSS 1938 p. 138) to Chile (Valparaiso), Juan Fernandez Islands and Australia (New South Wales.)

KEMP (1913 p. 107) suggested that the populations from Chile and Australia might represent different geographical races. This question was discussed at some length by SCHMITT (1940 pp. 181 ff.) who pointed out that the morphologically rather small differences in the shape of the telson which exist between Australian and West American specimens may be of higher taxonomical value than generally supposed. On the other hand the number of segments of the mandibular palp referred to by KEMP apparently is not taxonomically significant in the genus *Hemisquilla*, a different number of segments being sometimes found in the two palps of the same specimen.

The present specimen agrees with those from California and Chile examined by KEMP and SCHMITT in having but one lobe between the submedian and intermediate teeth of the telson. Like KEMP's specimen from Coquimbo it has mandibular palps consisting of three segments. In the absence of larger series of specimens both from

the Pacific coast of America and from Australia the decision upon a sub-specific division of the species must wait. The known range of the species on the coast of Chile is extended another three degrees of latitude from Coquimbo (abt. 30° S) to Valparaiso (abt. 33° S).

Lysiosquilla chilensis n.sp.

St. M 60. Southern Chile, Seno Reloncaví, south coast of Isla Tenglo. 41°30'15" S, 72°58'50" W. 29.III.1949. 13 specimens dug out of sandy beach at low water of spring tide.

Description of male, 28 mm: Carapace smooth with anteriolateral corners broadly rounded.

Eye-stalks not very broad, cornea comparatively small, more or less globular without bilobation, obliquely set, not much broader than the eye-stalk and only slightly overhanging on the outer stalk margin.

Rostral plate very nearly twice as broad as long with a small median point, anteriolateral corners broadly rounded.

Eye-stalks reaching to distal end of penultimate segment of antennular peduncle. Antennal peduncle and antennal scale shorter than eye-stalk; antennal peduncle reaching posterior margin of cornea on the median side, antennal scale reaching slightly past posterior margin of cornea on lateral side. No papilla were found on the antennal protopodite.

The dorsal margin of the raptorial carpus ends in a rather blunt tooth and close to it on the lateral margin there is another similar tooth. The inner margin of the raptorial propodos has four spines, one at the very corner at the carpal end with another, smaller one, close to it, and two long and slender spines close to where the ultimate and penultimate marginal spines of the raptorial dactylus come to rest when the dactylus is closed. Along the whole of the inner margin there are groups of setae or single setae set at comparatively large intervals. Raptorial dactylus with 17 spines, including the terminal one. On the convex side of the raptorial dactylus there are two blunt lobes near the proximal end.

Largest diameter of chela of 4th thoracic appendage nearly twice as long as that of 3rd appendage, that of 5th appendage approaching that of 3rd, but on the whole the chela of the 5th appendage is much more slender and narrow than that of the 3rd appendage.

Distal segment of outer ramus of last three pairs of thoracic appendages broadly ovate, although the last one is somewhat narrower than the two preceding ones and has the anterior margin nearly straight.

Abdomen with dorsal surface smooth and posterolateral corners of all but the last somite rounded. Last somite with posterolateral corner drawn out to form a long, pointed, and somewhat curved tooth.

Last uropod with the two spiniform processes of subequal length.

Dorsal margin of telson smooth, somewhat convex with two marginal teeth

Lysiosquilla chilensis n.sp. ♂ 28 mm. (type). To the left: Rostral plate (above), raptorial dactylus (centre), telson from ventral side (below). To the right: Uropod (above), sixth thoracical appendage (below).

(corresponding to lateral and intermediate teeth?). The basal parts of the row of submarginal (submediate) spines hidden when seen from the dorsal side. The spines number 12 on each side. There is another spine on the ventral side in front of the

Table 2

Lysiosquilla chilensis, survey of individual variations with respect to certain morphological features.

Length mm.	Spines on raptorial dactylus		Spines in submarginal row on telson	
	right	left	right	left
♂♂				
28 (type)	17	17	12	12
18	15	15	11	11
16	14	14	10	10
14	14	15	13	13
13	12	13	13	13
13	14	13	14	14
abt. 10 (mutilated)	—	—	—	—
♀♀				
28	14	16	13	13
28	17	15	12	12
17	15	15	—	—
13	14	14	12	12
12	13	13	13	13
10	12	12	13	13

lateral spine of the row. Between the submedian row and the first (?intermediate) marginal tooth there are three denticles, between this tooth and the second (?lateral) one there is one denticle.

Variations. The 13 specimens obtained measured from 10 to 28 mm in length. No sexual differences in the armature could be observed. The pattern of the armature of the raptorial appendages and of the telson of all the specimens was analyzed, and the results can be studied in table 2. It will be seen that while there is no apparent correlation between the number of submediate spines on the telson and the size of the specimen, the number of spines on the raptorial dactylus is, on the average, somewhat higher in the larger specimens, the maximum number of 17 occurring only in two of the largest ones. The arrangement of the spines on the raptorial propodus and on the lateral part of the telson is the same in all the examined specimens.

General remarks. Like *L. decemspinosa* RATHBUN, known to occur in Peru and in two localities in Costa Rica (cf. SCHMITT l. c.p. 190) it seems not unlikely that the present form represents a juvenile stage. It is, however, so characteristic that nothing remains but to describe it as a new species. It certainly is closely related to *L. decemspinosa*, having a large number of spines on the raptorial dactylus and a telson of very similar type. On the other hand it is easily distinguished by the broadly

Table 3

Distribution of Stomatopoda occurring on W coast of S. America.
(Mainly based upon SCHMITT 1940)

	Magellanic area	W Chile 40°S—52°S	Chile 30°S—40°S	Chile N of 30°S	Juan Fernandez Isl.	Peru	Ecuador	Colombia	C. American W coast	N. American W coast	N. American E coast	C. American E coast, West Indies	E coast of tropical S. America	E coast of Patagonia	S. Africa	Australia and N. Zealand	Remarks
<i>Squilla</i>																	
» <i>armata</i>	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	
» <i>gracilipes</i>	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
» <i>dubia</i>	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	
» <i>aculeata</i>	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
» <i>hancocki</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
» <i>panamensis</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	
» <i>parva</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
<i>Pseudosquilla</i>																	
» <i>oculata</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	{ Tropical E Pacific Indian Oc. Chile to 41°30'S
» <i>lessoni</i>	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	
<i>Hemisquilla</i>																	
» <i>stylifera</i>	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	Chile to 33°S
<i>Lysiosquilla</i>																	
» <i>polydactyla</i>	+(?)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
» <i>decemspinosa</i>	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
» <i>chilensis</i>	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
» <i>maculata</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	{ Tropical E Pacific Indian Oc.
<i>Gonodactylus</i>																	
» <i>oerstedii</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	
» <i>bahiahondensis</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
» <i>festae</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

ovate outer rami of the three last thoracic appendages, the still more numerous spines on the raptorial dactylus, and the different armature of the telson.

The combination of a telson with a smooth dorsal side and broadly ovate terminal joints of outer ramus of the posterior thoracic appendages is, as far as I know, unique within the genus.

A comparison with *L. capensis* HANSEN, of which species no satisfactory description still exists, seems desirable.

Ecology. The specimens were dug out of a sandy beach at low tide. No burrows could be definitely recognized as belonging to them. All of them were obtained by taking sand from the surface down to a depth of about one foot and sifting it. Four sampling areas of 0.25 sq. metres each yielded respectively 4, 4, 3, and 2 specimens.

Distribution of Stomatopoda of the Chilean coast

SCHMITT (1940) has given a full account of the Stomatopoda of the American West Coast, and the following brief summary is mainly based upon his paper, supplemented with a few data given by PORTER (1917) and the few new observations made by us. In table 3 are listed all species known to occur along the west coast of South America together with some information on their general distribution. Of the 17 species recorded from the area 7 have been found in Chile, including *Lysiosquilla polydactyla*, the exact finding place of which is still somewhat doubtful but believed to be Bahia Orange on Hoste Island south of Tierra del Fuego.

The various species may be conveniently divided into two groups within which a certain further sub-division seems possible.

I. Species restricted to the cool and temperate areas of the Chilean coast and having their northern limit somewhere between 30° S and 40° S.

a. Species possibly confined to the Magellanic and Patagonian areas (S. of approximately 40° S)

?*Lysiosquilla polydactyla*

?*Lysiosquilla chilensis*

b. Species also occurring along the coast of Central Chile, at least up to the Valparaiso area.

Squilla armata

Squilla gracilipes

II. Species with the centre of their distribution in the tropical or sub-tropical areas, in some cases entering the temperate waters of central Chile.

a. Species with their southern limit in Chile but N of 40° (42°), S or at Juan Fernandez Islands

Squilla aculeata

Pseudosquilla lessoni

Hemisquilla styliifera

b. Species with their southern limit in Peru

Squilla dubia

Lysiosquilla decemspinosa

c. Mainly tropical species not found S of Ecuador

Squilla hancocki

Squilla panamensis

Squilla parva

Pseudosquilla oculata

Lysiosquilla maculata

Gonodactylus oerstedii

Gonodactylus bahiahondensis

Gonodactylus festae

The concealed habits of numerous Stomatopoda and the difficulties involved in collecting many of the burrowing forms will probably make this list subject to future modification. However, it bears out the general impression obtained from other groups, viz. that the Magellanic and Patagonian area of the South American western and southern coasts is positively characterized and harbours a fauna clearly distinct from the tropical and subtropical fauna entering northern and central Chile (cf. HOLTHUIS 1952 pp. 96 ff.). Apparently the coast of central Chile and parts of northern Chile constitutes a transition area where more or less eurythermal northerly warm-water forms and southerly cold-water forms mix and live side by side while its positive characterization by endemic forms is poor indeed (cf. EKMAN 1953 p. 214).

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